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Study on Private Upper Secondary Education in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract

Private educational institutions are established by social organizations, socio-professional organizations, economic organizations or individuals when permitted by competent state agencies. The source of investment in the construction of infrastructures and the maintenance of operating funds of private educational institutions is the non-state budget. The main purpose of this study is to empirically test the private upper secondary education in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. The author collected secondary data from previous studies. The results of the research show that (i) Class and School size; (ii) Administrative officials and teachers; (iii) Facilities; (iv) Implementation of teaching and educating activities; including: The development of action plans; teaching activities; about extracurricular activities, job orientation and education outside the classroom. Based on the findings, some recommendations are given to improve the quality of private upper secondary education.

Keywords: Education, Private Upper Secondary, School, Class, Teacher

1. Introduction

Upper secondary education accepts students who have completed the lower secondary education program. During high school, students can transfer to an intermediate vocational training program if they wish and meet the requirements of the program. Upper secondary education is conducted for 3 school years, from 10th grade to 12th grade. High school graduates can go on to university or attend vocational education programs.

Private educational institutions are established by social organizations, socio-professional organizations, economic organizations or individuals when permitted by competent state agencies. The source of investment in the construction of infrastructures and the maintenance of operating funds of private educational institutions is the non-state budget.

General education plays a particularly important role, and is the cultural foundation of a country, the future of a nation, the basic premise for continuing, lifelong education to all individuals. Education at private high schools in Ho Chi Minh City has contributed to the general achievements of the city's education and training. The report on

the implementation results of the 9th Congress of the city committee's resolution stated that: Education - training has had positive movements; improved the quality of human resources.

The goal of general education is to help students develop comprehensively in virtue, mind, body, beauty and basic skills, develop personal capacity, dynamism, creativity, and shape human personality of socialist Vietnam, build citizenship status and responsibilities. The ultimate objective of general education is to have every citizen prepare for the process of studying or living, working, participating in the construction and defense of the fatherland.

The budget for investment in education - training increases every year. The state has made many improvements in education – training, such as: developing the spacious and modern facilities and infrastructure; standardizing the contingent of teachers in all disciplines and levels of study; innovates teaching methods, which focus on personality, lifestyle, moral and ideal education for students. The socialization of education - training achieved positive results; the non-public education and training system contributes significantly to human resource training; the management of education - training is innovated actively and effectively; the role of family in the cooperation with the school and society in educating the young generation is promoted; the quality of teaching and learning has been improved, which is the basis for the fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training in Ho Chi Minh City.

Vietnam has its own characteristics in terms of institutions, is a developing country which approaches a socialist-oriented market economy and is in the process of international integration. Thanks to the innovation policy, the process of educational socialization and the development of the private school system have also developed. From the above reasons, research on private upper secondary education in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam is necessary and meaningful.

2. Theoretical Background and Literature Review

In the world, private general education has developed very early and there have been many researches on private general education, namely

James and Benjamin (1988) studied public and private schools in Japan and the ways in which they interacted to create Japan's widespread education. Political goals have influenced the size of public schools and the influence of the labor market on the education sector has attracted investors. They mainly make investments in the Japanese private education sector, in which the high school and higher education are paid more attention. The authors carried out a very elaborate and exhaustive study of Japan's educational policy options. The Japanese government has succeeded in creating a congruence between the public and private sectors in education (James & Benjamin, 1988)

Le Grand and Bartlett (1993) argued that the education industry market is an accepted term in education. It is a special market, which is different from the market for goods or the market in other areas of services. In the education market, besides the competition mechanism and private education providers, the state still plays the leading role in education provision, quality control, and protection of learners' interests to ensure the social equity in education (Le Grand & Bartlett, 1993)

Lockheed and Jimenez (1994) study the reality of the public-private balance in education and the policy debates on this issue. The authors compare the performance of public and private schools in five developing countries with diverse educational backgrounds: Colombia, Dominican Republic, Philippines, Tanzania and Thailand. The authors also focused their differential analysis on input, process and school management in two ways: using available data and directly gathering insights from a small sample of public and private schools in these five countries. Research has an important influence on public education policy when it is confirmed that public schools can be effective by applying the management style of private schools (Lockheed and Jimenez, 1994)

Wolff et al. (2005) assessed how public policies in the region affect the performance of private schools. The authors describe the current state of policies and relationships between the public and private sectors in education in six countries: Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Guatemala, Peru and Venezuela. Research results confirm the

importance of private education and the concept of "privatization" in education is an outdated concept. To be more specific, the difference between public and private schools is less important than the recognized public interests of each. With the right policies, high-quality public education can coexist with the development of private education. The authors also point out that, contrary to common assumptions, private education not only serves the well-off but also the poor and needy classes in society (Wolff et al., 2005).

Besides international studies, there have been a few domestic studies on this topic. Some of notable researches are mentioned below:

Glewwe and Patrinos (1988) used survey data in Vietnam to collect the reasons why households choose public or private schools for their children and the costs and benefits of private schools. The study analyzed the current situation of non-public education (NPE) in Vietnam and analyzed the impact of economic, social and geographical factors on non-public education (NPE). Research results show that well-off households in Vietnam are less likely to choose private schools, but tend to choose private schools for their children to attend when their income is low. An increase in family incomes can lead to an increase in their willingness to spend on education. Religion and ethnicity have little influence on the choice of public or private school. In addition, in terms of salary policy, employees working for private schools will receive higher wages than employees working for public schools (Glewwe & Patrinos, 1988).

Dan (1998) has pointed out the theoretical and practical bases for building the regulation of private high schools such as: the viewpoint of the Party on education and educational socialization, the role of social participation in education, the actual status of organization and operation of private high schools before the year 2000.

Anh (2006) analyzed and assessed the current situation of NPE schools majoring in preschool, general education, and professional education in Hanoi from the time of renovation to 2004 and proposed solutions to strengthen, develop NPE schools. The author presented the results achieved by NPE schools majoring in preschool, high school, and professional education in Hanoi such as: The growth in the number of schools, the number of students, development of facilities, innovation of educational content and methods. In addition, the author pointed out weaknesses such as: the management capacity of the Board of Directors, the principal and the lack of a permanent teaching staff; quality of education; inadequacies in state management of preschool, general education and professional education schools in Hanoi. From that, the author has proposed a series of solutions to strengthen and develop NPE schools.

The above research topics have overviewed the development of the private high school system in some localities and countries; the role and position of the private high school system; clarified the market factors of private education services and pointed out some inadequacies in the current educational management mechanism. Inheriting the results of the above studies, this study analyzes and evaluates private high school education in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

3. Methodology

This study uses qualitative research methods. The author used techniques of synthesis, analysis, comparison to evaluate the private high school education in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. In addition, the author collected previous studies. Qualitative research methods orientated and refined the research results of previous studies; from there, this study inherited and applied.

4. Research Result and Discussion

4.1. Class and School size

Since 1996, on average, 3 to 5 new schools have been founded every year. In the school year 2004 - 2005, the Department of Education and Training (DOET) managed 36 non-public high schools, including 29 people-founded schools and 07 private schools. In the total of 22,735 students of these schools, the number of students registering permanent residence outside the city is 12,467. Non-public high schools are mainly located in urban and suburban districts.

From the school year 2005-2006 to the school year 2009 -2010, educational socialization policies were implemented, and to accommodate the increasing demand of students from the city as well as other provinces, non-public high schools were rapidly developing in terms of both quality and quantity. In this period, according to provisions of the charter of high schools, several people-founded high schools went through a transition process to become private schools, which resulted in a decreasing number of people-founded schools, together with an average increase of 4 to 5 new private schools every year. This period recorded the most rapid increase of the number of students in non-public high schools (including those from other provinces) since 2005 till now. As a result, 41 new private high schools were founded during this time, and students' education needs were fulfilled. The number of non-public schools witnessed the most significant increase in three years: 2009 with 10 new schools were founded; 2010 with 15 new schools; 2011 with 12 new schools.

By the end of the school year 2009-2010, the total number of non-public high schools in the city was 73, including 11 people-founded and 62 private schools, with the total number of students being 33,730; including 16,267 students whose permanent household residence registration was outside the city. The development of private high school quantity (from 2005 to 2014) is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: The development of private high school quantity (from 2005 to 2014)

Sources: HoChiMinh city' Department of Education and Training (2015)

The development of the number of students in the city is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The development of the number of students in the city (from 2005 to 2015)

Sources: HoChiMinh city' Department of Education and Training (2015)

By the school year 2015 - 2016, there were 85 private high schools in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), with more than 100 institutions in all districts. Among them, 18 schools comprised 3 levels: primary - secondary – high school and 36 comprised 2 levels: secondary and high school. There were 31,968 high school students, with 1,056 classes in total (30.3 students per class on average) from all districts (see table 1).

Table 1: Statistics results of private schools/classes/students in Ho Chi Minh City

District	Quantily	Quantily of classes				Quantily of students			
		Total	Inside			Total	Inside		
			10' class	11' class	12' class		10' class	11' class	12' class
1	04	75	36	27	12	1.524	758	530	236
2	01	3	1	1	1	50	18	20	12
3	02	12	5	5	2	273	110	123	40
5	04	51	23	19	9	1.447	722	513	212
6	04	34	17	11	6	893	508	251	134
7	04	45	20	16	9	1,176	576	415	185
9	02	48	22	15	11	1,421	647	455	319
10	03	42	22	13	7	1.016	519	336	161
11	04	105	50	34	21	3.563	1.742	1.158	663
12	06	62	30	17	15	1,763	899	485	379
Go Vap	09	86	39	26	21	2.764	1.347	831	586
Tan Binh	10	202	75	67	60	7.811	2.979	2.650	2.182
Tan Phu	16	191	85	57	49	5.703	2.734	1.652	1.317
Binh Thanh	04	15	8	5	2	384	210	130	44
Phu Nhuan	03	17	6	6	5	293	109	103	81
Thu Duc	02	25	10	9	6	645	300	209	136
Binh Tan	05	37	18	11	8	1,177	613	323	241
Binh Chanh	02	6	3	2	1	65	31	19	15
Total	85	1,056	470	341	245	31,968	14,822	10,203	6,943

Sources: HoChiMinh city' Department of Education and Training (2015)

In the total of 31, 968 students, the number of students whose permanent household residence was registered outside the city is 12,833 (accounting for 40.1%). Students were not evenly distributed among all the schools, as 29 schools had fewer than 100 students.

Some schools with a large number of students are Nguyen Khuyen Secondary and High School with 5,589 students; Truong Vinh Ky Secondary & High School with 3,208 students; Hong Ha Secondary and High School with 1,277 students; Hong Duc Secondary and High School with 1,002 students.

Schools with foreign elements mainly admitted foreign students and employed foreign courses. To meet the demand of the society, a few schools were in experiment to gain permission for admitting Vietnamese students, such as Khai Sang Primary, Secondary and High School, Anh Viet International Primary, Secondary and High School, International School Ho Chi Minh City (Binh, 2002).

The learning outcomes of students in private high schools is demonstrated as follows:

In the school year 2005 - 2006, the number of students with learning outcomes ranked as excellent was 3,222 (14.2% of all students), as good was 8,531 (37.5%), as average was 9,960(43.8%), as weak/poor is 1,022(4.5%); The high school graduation rate was over 95%, some schools achieved a 100% rate.

In the school year 2009 - 2010, a total of 4,871 students (14.5%) were ranked as excellent in learning outcomes; 14,176 (42.0%) were ranked as good; 14,353 (42.6%) were ranked as average; and 330 (0.9%) were received a weak/poor ranking. It can be observed that the rate of excellent and good students had increased, while the rate of graduation had remained stable.

In the school year 2013 - 2014, the number of students with learning outcomes ranked as excellent was 10,964 (27.1%); as good was 17,907 (44.2%); as average was 10,649 (26.3%); as weak/poor was 994 (2.4%). Several schools achieved a 100% high school graduation rate thanks to their continuous efforts to enhance education quality.

The learning outcomes of students in private high schools (see figure 3):

Figure 3: The learning outcomes of students in private high schools

Sources: HoChiMinh city' Department of Education and Training (2015)

With the current trajectory, to satisfy the demand for educational revolutionising, many private high schools are implementing different methods to further improve teaching quality, prominently: Ngo Thoi Nhiem Primary, Secondary & High School; Nguyen Khuyen Primary, Secondary & High School, etc.

4.2. Administrative officials and teachers

According to statistics for the school year 2015 - 2016, there were 216 officials on administrative duty in private schools in HCMC (2.6 officials per school on average). The number of administrators varied from 1 - 6, depending on the scale of the school. Noticeably, a few schools had 5 vice principals, such as Duc Tri Secondary & High School, Nguyen Khuyen Secondary & High School.

In recent years, administrators in private schools mostly used to be former-officials at public schools, who are in good health and have experience in operating schools. Moreover, private high schools have paid close attention to fostering the next generations of officials by sending teachers to take professional training courses in school administration; thus, younger administrators with management skills, creativity and dynamism to operate schools have been appointed.

According to the statistics for the school year 2015 - 2016, the number of teachers in private schools in HCMC was 3,384 (3.2 teachers per class on average); among them, 14.5% had university or higher degrees (Central

Committee of Thought and Culture, 2001). Some schools also appointed specialized teachers in positions of managing the school's Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union & HCM Young pioneers Organization.

Teachers of private schools are recruited from a variety of backgrounds such as freelance teachers, retired teachers, or visiting teachers from public schools. Some schools use foreign teachers to teach foreign languages and life skills education topics. Most of the teachers of private schools are formally trained to meet and exceed standards; have a high sense of responsibility; be enthusiastic about their job; gain experience in teaching; be passionate for their profession; care for students; consciously train their ethics, political qualities, lifestyle; always study to improve qualifications and teaching efficiency.

4.3. Facilities

According to the statistics of the school year 2015-2016, the total number of non-public classrooms is 1,583; 1,529 of which are secured and durable.

In general, facilities such as classrooms, equipment, libraries, etc. are becoming more and more invested for the sake of the students' learning. In their development history, many schools have purchased new teaching equipment to meet standards, such as: Ngo Thoi Nhiem Primary, Secondary and High School; Nguyen Khuyen Primary, Secondary and High School; Bac My Secondary and High School; Ngoi Sao Secondary and High School; Tri Duc Secondary and High School; Nhan Van Secondary and High School; Thanh Binh Primary, Secondary and High School; Sao Viet Secondary and High School; Duy Tan Secondary and High School; Hoa Binh High School; Hong Duc Secondary and High School; Van Hanh Primary, Secondary and High school, etc. However, a few schools still had to rent facilities, which are buildings renovated into teaching facilities with relatively adequate equipment, good teaching service conditions and commitment to develop with the schools after 5 years of operation. In addition, schools with foreign elements have a large ground area, and a lot of investment in facilities, which makes their classrooms more spacious, clean and good-looking. Most of the schools can adequately provide the facilities for accommodation and daily activities for boarding students at the schools.

4.4. Implementation of teaching and educating activities

4.4.1. The development of action plans

Every year, in accordance with the orientation of the Department of Education and Training, private high schools develop and organize plans in order to achieve teaching and educational goals according to the school year objectives. Different types of plans that can be developed and implemented include: School year plan; Political and Ideological Education plan; Professions plan; extra-curricular plan; Plan for vocational training and careers guidance; 02 sessions/day teaching plan, etc. All these plans are inspected and approved by the Department of Education and Training.

4.4.2. Teaching activities

Schools have to follow national curriculum pursuant to Decision No.16/2006/QĐ-BGDĐT on December 5, 2006 by the Ministry Of Education and Training (MOET) regarding knowledge and skill standards as well as required attitudes. From the 2011-2012 school year onwards, content for each subject has been subtly moderated pursuant to Official Dispatch No. 5842/BGDĐT-VP on September 1, 2011 by MOET to conform to knowledge and skill education standards, teaching duration and other region-specific conditions.

Schools devise and implement an educational plan that is aimed to develop students' capabilities in terms of knowledge, skill and attitude standards of each educational stage in the general education program within the universal 37-week school year timeframe as instructed by the MOET, and to ensure adequate time for the training, revising, experimenting and exercising along with organizing on-the-field and creative activities as well as periodic assessments.

Schools with adequate staff and facilities and the approval of students' families also provide, besides the 2 sessions per day curriculum, a certain number of optional courses related to official subjects, and supplementary classes for foreign language, computer science and other important subjects.

Additionally, several integrated educational topics are implemented in accordance with MOET 's guide: Morals education, Moral examples of President Ho Chi Minh; Law Education; Anti-corruption Education; Education of National Sovereignty On Borderlands, Sea and Islands; Economical and effective energy use guides; Environment protection; Biological Diversity And Natural Conservation; Handling, preventing and alleviating consequences of climate change and natural disasters; Traffic safety education; Heritages studies.

Teaching methods receive more and more modification with a view to bolstering positivity, proactivity and creativity in students; replacing the one-sided indoctrination and rote memory method; improving student's application of knowledge and skills; teaching mindset and manner and self-study; ensuring a balance of academic education and behavior education; classifying students based on knowledge and skill standards of the general education program; diversifying learning methods, especially with practical, creative and scientific activities; promoting information technology and multimedia application in teaching and learning. The application of skills and knowledge in problem-solving could fundamentally develop students' abilities, which helps students determine their attitudes and motivations to learn.

Students and teachers are oriented to actively take part in learning, teaching and exchanging information in the online archive called "Interactive School" by MOET in favor of Official dispatch No. 3535/BGDDT-GDTrH of May 27, 2013 regarding "Research-based Learning" and other positive teaching methods; MOET's Official dispatch No.5555/BGDDT-GDTrH of October 8, 2014. Problem solving, practical skills and project-based learning are encouraged to be integrated in school subjects. STEM education - Science, Technology, Engineering and Math - are also integrated and applied more and more in related subjects of the general education program. Testing and assessment based on the orientation of developing students' competencies and qualities have been innovated. All forms of testing and assessment are designed to boost students' abilities, as the assessment can be used to support students with learning methods, encourage and motivate students. Posing questions is also under strict and serious supervision in accordance with the regulations at all stages, including supervising, marking and commenting and evaluating students, to ensure objectivity, honesty, fairness, proper assessment of students' ability and progress. Formative assessment also receives a great deal of attention: classroom assessment; assessment by records; assessment by observation; project and presentation evaluation; and assessment results should include progress evaluation and summative assessments at the end of each semester. There should be a flexible combination of subjective and objective tests, theoretical and practical tests. Test structure should be strictly followed; and multi-select objective questions with multiple correct answers are advised to replace single-select questions. Software and applications are developed to prepare and manage test and exam questions, and to construct a "testing and evaluation question bank". It is also important to develop an "Open learning materials archive" of high-quality questions, exercises, exam questions, lesson plans, and reference materials on the websites of the Ministry of Education and Training (<http://truongtructuyen.edu.vn/>).

Most schools have promoted the application of information technology in management and teaching, such as: Electronic scoring books in accordance with the guidance of official Dispatch No. 3260 / GDDT-GDTrH dated 09/10/2015 of Ho Chi Minh City Department of Education and Training; Management staff, teachers and children are better equipped with projectors, interactive whiteboards; E-learning-oriented software to assist in preparing lesson plan with a view to improving the information technology skills and capabilities of educational management staff, teachers and students; the implementation of advanced teaching methods: interactive teaching on the Internet environment, E-learning, simple and friendly software for creating online lectures (for examples: Adobe Presenter, i-Spring and Articulate) It is also encouraged to hold competitions on the application of information and communication technology in teaching and learning such as the "Designing E-learning lecture records" contest, the "Innovative teachers with information technology" etc organized by the MOET.

4.4.3. About extracurricular activities, job orientation and education outside the classroom

Institutions also pay great attention to literature-physical-beauty, ethics, consciousness, ideals, and ambitions of students by organizing extracurricular activities, career guidance, after-school hours, outdoor activities, etc. which induce students' comprehensive mental and physical growth.

Vocational training activities for students are carried out according to the general education program promulgated under Decision No. 16/QĐ-BGDĐT dated May 5th, 2006 and current guiding documents of the MOET with a total of 9 lessons/school year including 3 themes: (i) September theme: The youth study and train for the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country; (ii) December theme: The youth construct and defend the country; (iii) March theme: The youth with career development.

Some schools consult with the party committees and local authorities to mobilize businesses, socio-economic entities, universities, colleges, etc. to participate in the process of vocational education for students.

Extra-curricular activities are integrated with a number of contents according to the document No. 3092/GDDT-TrH dated September 4th, 2014 of the Department of Education and Training and include 2 lessons/month during regular school hours according to 9 topics specified in the school year. The homeroom teacher guides and advises students to independently organize and administer activities during extra-curricular hours.

Many schools have arranged extra-curricular activities for students with creative and practical content and forms. For example: Viet Uc High School organized a talk show for students with Mr. George F. Smoot who won the 2006 Nobel Prize in Physics at the International University - Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City; held a meeting with the New Zealand Embassy at the February 3 campus; organized a visit to the Thermal Power Plant in Ba Ria; Viet My Anh High School organized for students to visit the Ceramic Factory; Bamboo Village conservation area in Binh Duong province; Viet My High School organized a trip for students to visit and study at the candy factory and beekeeping facility in Ben Tre province; Viet Au High School organized an extra-curricular activities program in which students in Nha Trang visited the historical site of Ben Duoc temple in Cu Chi; Van Lang High School organized excursions with extracurricular learning activities for students.

5. Conclusion

The current situation of private upper secondary education in Ho Chi Minh City has achieved remarkable results, specifically as follows:

Achievements:

The network of private schools and classes is developed in accordance with the local situation, meeting the learning needs of the local students and students from other provinces. Many new schools were built in the direction of solidification and standardization. Facilities and equipment are invested and enhanced synchronously and modernly to meet the needs of teaching and learning.

Teaching and educational activities are organized to ensure compliance with industry regulations. Learning and training results are increasingly improved.

Managers, teachers and staff of the schools are insufficient number, dedicated to the profession, responsible, dynamic, creative, active in teaching activities and participating in emulation movements. The management and teaching capacity is constantly improved.

The reason of the above results, first of all, is due to the political stability, the socio-economic development achievements of the city. They have created the foundation for the development of education in general and private education in particular. The City Department of Education and Training has been closely involved in directing, managing and organizing the implementation of tasks; implemented programs and subjects according to the standards of knowledge and skills, ensuring flexibility, fit, suitable for students and reality; implemented innovation of teaching methods; strengthened inspection and supervision of teaching activities at private schools. The majority of administrators and teachers are enthusiastic always uphold the sense of responsibility and do their best to overcome difficulties and complete tasks.

Besides the achieved results, private high school education in Ho Chi Minh City still has limitations such as:

Resolution of the 10th Party Congress of Ho Chi Minh City for the term 2015-2020 has assessed the city's education and training: The quality of education and training has not yet met the needs of development and integration. Educational content and methods are slow to innovate, not linked to reality. The teaching staff and education management staff have not met the needs in terms of quantity and quality. Management of educational activities of NPE has not met the requirements. The construction of a learning society has not been substantive, which has low results (Y, 1999).

The quality of education has been gradually improved, but not high yet. The work of traditional education, moral and ideal education has not been focused. There are still many students with average academic ability, lack in quality and morality, showing many signs of violating school rules, being playful, lazy to study, dishonest in exams.

Managers and teachers are recruited from many different sources with unequal professional qualifications. Some are not bold and actively innovate in management as well as in teaching. The capacity of managers is not up to the task requirements. Management in some schools is still loose, subjective and not very effective. The number of permanent teachers is still small. Most of the teachers are contract teachers, and they frequently change jobs. There are, so, many difficulties in operating and directing professional activities. Some administrators and teachers are still hesitant to innovate, not proactive when just waiting for the guidance of their superiors. They maintain their one-way-imposition management style and teaching methods, which just focus on knowledge transmission and assessment, but not focus on developing students' capacity. This limits students' ability to be active and proactive. Entrance students often have weak academic performance, poor behavior. Students frequently move in and out during the school year, leading to the continuous fluctuations in the number of students at the school. Students do not have the appropriate learning motivation. Many students are affected by social networks and external factors, so there are still some negative manifestations in their lifestyle, in the way they behave with people around, and in their awareness of social ethical standards.

Teaching facilities and equipment in some schools are not enough to meet teaching needs.

The reasons for these limitations are:

Perceptions, psychology and actions of some administrators and teachers on educational innovation have not been consistent with practical requirements; the lack of being active and proactive in carrying out the task of fundamentally and comprehensively renewing school education as required by Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW of the Eighth Conference of the Central Executive Committee, XI.

The capacity of some school administrators is not enough to meet the current educational reform requirements, the management skills and qualifications are limited. Most work based on personal experience, not using development strategy and operational plans. The working style is still awkward, some managers are still not proactive, not creative, but just rely on the instructions of their superiors. They are still slow to solve problems, have no flexibility in management. Their ability to persuade the public is still limited and the working method has not really met the requirements of the task.

Some teachers have the mindset of being a staff, lack of enthusiasm. They have not made effort in teaching and educational activities, or tried to cultivate and practice moral qualities and professional capacity. Their skills in using equipment, gadgets and information technology application in teaching are still limited. They hardly make innovation in teaching methods. All of these reasons mentioned above lead to low quality of teaching.

The coordination between school, family and society is not really effective. The negatives in society strongly affect the awareness and lifestyle of young people while many parents are not aware of the importance of education. Others have difficult circumstances, so they are not really aware of the critical value of education and helping their children with studying. Many students' parents are busy with business, pay little attention to students, do not have time to remind and guide them in study and in daily life. There are also many cases of parents' helplessness in raising children, letting the education institutions take all of such responsibility.

In addition, because it is a private school, the funds provided by the Board of Directors are mainly for salaries, while the budgets for movement and commendation activities are very limited. This leads to the lack of encouragement for teachers and students, not promoting teaching-studying emulation activities effectively. Some state management mechanisms and policies for private schools also have many shortcomings, causing many obstacles to the development of schools.

Therefore, the Ho Chi Minh City government needs to have many specific policies to create favorable conditions for private schools to access land rental to build and expand the size of schools and classes; ensure equality between public and private schools; improve the quality of management apparatus in schools; renovate the teaching materials; strengthen the state management for NPE high schools in the area. In addition, the Board of Directors of non-public education schools should pay more attention to movement activities and improve incomes for employees (administrative department, teachers). Furthermore, administrators and teachers must always improve their professional capacity, enthusiasm for the profession, innovation and creativity in order to improve the quality of education.

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